

A METHOD OF RELIABILITY ANALYSIS FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The authors of this paper present a full quantity loading method for reliability analysis of composite structural system in consideration of degradation of the structural stiffness. According to the values of utilization ratios of members, critical members can be found out. The way of composing the critical members in groups is adopted to enumerate and identify significant failure modes. Then, a fault tree of structural system is constituted. Some kinds of principles of deletion and mergence of failure modes are used, so computing failure probability of system is greatly simplified, some illustrative examples show that the method are very efficient. For large scale composite structural system its advantages are especially obvious.

INTRODUCTION

In reliability analysis of structural system, finding out an efficient method to enumerate and identify significant failure modes is crucial problem. It may save computer running time and decrease probability of losing significant failure modes. Specifically, it is very important for larger scale of structural system. Some articles have been published in this area for the structural system with metal materials. All these methods can be divided into two types. One is solving fault tree problem by network optimization theory¹⁻². Another is finding out critical members by method of optimal criterion³ or method of engineering criterion⁴.

For reliability analysis of the laminate, full quantity loading method is presented by this paper's author⁵.

In this paper authors should 1) research on method of reliability analysis of structural systems which are constituted by the composite materials or the mixture of composite and metal materials, 2) find out a significant mode for enumerating and identifying significant failure modes of these structural system.

COMPUTING METHOD OF ULTIMATE STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL SYSTEM

The model of composite structural system is divided into discrete elements. The layer-group is taken as basic member in the procedure of stress analysis of structure.

The composite structure is brittle one, after some members partially damaged they can not return to original condition. In other words, when loading exceeds a certain value which is the first peak of load-displacement curve the larger deformation of structure should occur. Because of these the first peak load of load-displacement curve is usually

taken as the maximum capability of loading of structure in engineering. This usual method is still used in this paper.

Finite element method is adopted to carry out stress analysis of structure. For each member its serious degree of loading may be judged by strength criterion. With the occurrence of failure members, the structural global stiffness is changed. Under the original general loading, if the residual structure is no longer appearing new failure members, the structure is in a steady condition and it can be continuously loaded. When the general loading increases up to a certain value, the stipulated loss efficacy index of structure is reached. Corresponding to this condition, the loading is taken as maximum capability of loading. i.e. structural ultimate strength.

In order to simplify computation approximate method is used. That is, the failure members are treated group by group. When a member failed, the change of the global stiffness of structure is very small, so the global stiffness may be considered as invariable. When number of failure members is M, their member stiffness are degraded and the global stiffness is modified each time. According to this method it will take fewer computer running time and obtain certain precision as reasonable value of M selected.

FULL QUANTITY LOADING METHOD WITH A CHANGE IN STIFFNESS FOR RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL SYSTEM

As mentioned above, the ultimate strength of structure, in fact, represents the maximum capability of loading corresponding to the most serious failure mode. In reliability of structural system since load and structural strength both are random variables, usually not only the most serious failure sequence of system is considered but also more serious failure sequence are considered as significant failure modes. These significant failure modes can be shown in a form of fault tree. Full quantity loading method with a change in stiffness is presented in this paper. In this method utilization ratio is taken as a basis of judgement for enumerating significant failure modes. The principal points and steps of this method are illustrated as follows.

(1) Under a certain general loading the finite element method is used to carry out stress analysis of structure. There may be two models. In one of them the layer-group is taken as basis member, as mentioned above, the composite structure is separated along surface and thickness, then, off-axis stress components in each layer-group plane are solved. In the another model the laminate is taken as a member, i.e. the structure is separated only along surface, so average stress components of laminate along thickness are obtained. According to stiffness value of each layer-group at the loading direction, off-axis stress components of each layer-group can be solved. The off-axis stress components are transformed into on-axis one. Then, they are substituted to strength criterion, for example, Tsai-Hill criterion (other criterion can also be selected). It can be expressed as

$$(\sigma_1/X)^2 + (\sigma_2/Y)^2 - \sigma_1\sigma_2/X^2 + (\tau_{12}/S)^2 = R \quad (1)$$

where σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} are on-axis stress components in plane of any layer-group, and X, Y and S are longitudinal, transverse and shear strength respectively.

If R is larger than or equals to 1.0, it means that the layer-group fails. R is called the utilization ratio of member. Under a certain general loading the utilization ratio of each member can be obtained respectively.

(2) Finding out the most and more serious critical member. the utilization ratios of all members are arranged in size sequence from large to small. And their maximum value is R_{max} .

$$R_{max} = \max (R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n) \quad (2)$$

where n is total number of all members. If R_{max} equals to 1.0, it means that the most serious critical member just fails. Corresponding to this case the general loading on the structure is called critical general loading P_0 .

Let S_i be the ratio of utilization ratio R_i of i member to R_{max} and constant C denotes selected range of more critical members. It can be shown as

$$S_i = R_i / R_{max} \quad (3)$$

$$1 \geq S_i \geq C \quad (4)$$

The value of constant C may be taken as about 0.8 to 0.9. Therefore, the formula (4) is a criterion for selecting critical members. On the basis of formula (4) the number n_1 of critical member are selected which include the most and more serious members.

(3) These critical members are composed to obtain various significant failure modes, so they can be shown in a form of fault tree of structural system.

ND members are choosed in turn among all critical members which are arranged in value of S_i sequence. Their member stiffness are certainly degraded. According to the sequence of S_i the (M - ND) members are among other critical members. They are combined with ND members into some gourps. These are still M members in each group. The stiffness of members in each group is degraded respectively. So the first class branches of fault tree are constituted. After the load increased the method of selecting critical members n_2 of the second class is similar to the above. Therefore, the second class branches of fault tree are constituted. In accordance with this way every class branches of the fault tree are obtained.

(4) Some principles for deletion and mergence of failure modes. In the way of composition in groups the number of significant failure modes is still quite large. some principles to simplify computation of failure probability of system are presented. They are as follows.

i) There are L1 failure modes. In these modes structural collapse is caused by failure of the same members, and the ultimate strengthes of the modes are the same. It means that these modes are completely relative. Correlation coefficients ρ_{ij} between these kinds of two failure modes i and j equal to one. So it is only necessary to retain one significant failure mode and (Li-1) modes can be deleted.

ii) there are L2 failure modes. In these modes structural collapse is caused by failure of different members, and the ultimate strengthes of the modes are the same. It is shown that failure probability P_i (i=1-L2) of single mode are the same and correlation coefficient ρ_{ij} between two failure modes are the same. So a method can be used in which probability is multiplied by some coefficient to simplify computation of probability of system. It can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma P_i &= L2 \times P_i \\ \Sigma P_{ij} &= [L2(L2-1) - \sum_{k=1}^{L2-1} (L2-k)] P_{ij} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where P_i and P_{ij} are failure probability of single mode and joint probability between two modes respectively.

iii) There are L3 failure modes, in these modes, structural collapse is caused by failure of members, approximate to each other, and the strengths of the modes are approaching, that is, difference of the values not exceeds some range, for example, 1-2%. It may be neglected. So L3 failure modes are considered as completely relative and correlation coefficient ρ_{ij} equals to 1.0. Then, they can be merged by the principle i).

ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE

In order to decrease quantity of computation a mixed structure is taken as example for illustrating the method of reliability analysis and enumerating significant failure modes.

(1) Data of property (Table 1)

(2) Selection of parameters

Parameters C, M and ND are choosed as 0.9, 5 and 2. Let coefficient of variation of load and ultimate strength be 0.2 and 0.1 respectively.

(3) The loss efficacy indexes of structure

Loss efficacy indexes of strength:

i) If all members through a laminate fail, this case is called 'a hole'. When such a hole appears in structure it may be considered as a loss efficacy index.

ii) The ratio of failed composite members to total number of composite members reaches 20%.

iii) The first peak of load-displacement curve appears, i.e. $P_i \leq P_{i-1}$. Loss efficacy indexes of stiffness:

i) Ratio of increased displacement of structure is larger than ratio of increased loading. It can be expressed as

$$(\mu_i - \mu_{i-1})/\mu_i \geq \eta \times (P_i - P_{i-1})/P_i \quad (6)$$

where η may be taken as 2.0, i is some load step and μ_i is structural displacement at some point.

ii) Maximum relative flexibility exceeds certain value. It is shown as

$$(V_j/X_j)_{\max} \geq \bar{f} \quad (7)$$

where x_j is the longitudinal coordinate at point of maximum flexibility, v_j is the displacement at this point and \bar{f} is the limit value of relative flexibility. In this example it is taken as 0.2.

iii) Maximum torsion angle of structure exceeds certain value, i.e.

$$\varphi_{\max} \geq \varphi_0 \quad (8)$$

where φ_0 is the limit value of torsion angle. In this example it is taken as 5° .

Other loss efficacy index: Structure can not carry loading. This case is caused by some members failed in certain place, for example, some bar fails at loading direction.

(4) Example

Multi-walls structure made of composite material skin and metallic skeleton is shown in Fig. 1.

1) Construction and finite element model

Number [1]-[16] are metallic bar elements with constant axial force.

Number [1]-[28] are metallic shearing panel elements. Number [1]-[24] are composite quadrangle panel elements with plane stress (data neglected).

- 2) Mean value of load equals to 2920 lb.
- 3) Enumerating significant failure modes of system. Part branches of fault tree are shown in Fig.2.
- 4) deletion and mergence of significant failure modes.

The 1st to sixth branches are taken as example. For these six modes the structural collapses are caused by failure of different members but their ultimate strength are the same, so they belong to principle ii) as mentioned above. The computation of failure probability of system can be simplified by equation (5), where L2 equals to 6. Equation (5) can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma P_i &= 6P_i \\ \Sigma P_{ij} &= [6 \times 5 - \sum_{k=1}^5 (6-k)] P_{ij} = 18P_{ij} \end{aligned}$$

In Fig.2 the lower branches are compared with the upper six branches. Differences of ultimate strength of system are less than 1%, so they belong to principle iii) and can be merged.

The middle branches and upper six branches are all the same, so they belong to principle i) and can be deleted. After treatment of deletion and mergence, there are only six modes in Fig.2.

CONCLUSIONS

(1) Because composite structure is very complex, simplification treatment is needed for computing reliability of system. The full quantity loading method with a change in stiffness is used and parameter c, M and ND are properly choosed, so that it may take fewer computer running time and obtain better precision, The way of composing critical members in groups may raise greatly efficiency of computation. These advantages are illustrated by some examples. It is shown that for reliability analysis of composite structure this method is reasonable.

(2) Some principles of deletion and mergence are adopted so computation work of failure probability P_{st} is simplified for enumerating significant failure modes of system. It is shown that the method presented by this paper is very efficient. For large scale structure its effect is especially obvious.

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Table 1

Property Data

Al-Alloy			B/E	
E_1	10.5×10^6	$1b/in^2$	30×10^6	$1b/in^2$
E_2	10.5×10^6	$1b/in^2$	2.7×10^6	$1b/in^2$
G_{12}	4.038×10^6	$1b/in^2$	0.7×10^6	$1b/in^2$
ν_{12}	0.30		0.21	
$[\sigma]$	100×10^3	$1b/in^2$	X_t	128×10^3
$[\tau]$	60×10^3	$1b/in^2$	X_c	128×10^3
			Y_t	6.93×10^3
			Y_c	26.6×10^3
			S	10.2×10^3

Fig.1 Multi-walls structure made of composite material skin and metallic skeleton.

Fig.2 Part of branches of fault tree of the Example

(In Fig.2 failure member is shown as m_1, m_2 , where m_2 is the number of failure member, and m_1 is the number of laminate plate which includes this failure member)

4. Miscellaneous

